

STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE TEXT OF
APPLICATIONS IN FRENCH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14508341>

Abstract: This article provides a detailed explanation of the theoretical and practical foundations of writing formal applications. The structure, main parts, and content of applications are expressed in a formal style, reflecting social and hierarchical relationships. In particular, the use of politeness forms (la formule de politesse) in applications written in French is analyzed, depending on the status of the recipient. Expressions that serve to express respect and politeness, their hierarchical order, and the context of use are explained through examples. This guide is aimed at improving the process of writing applications, covering grammatical and pragmatic aspects. In particular, the correct choice of the level of respect and taking into account hierarchical relationships in the process of writing applications increases the chances of achieving the applicant's goal.

Keywords: Application, official document, la formule de politesse, level of respect, hierarchical relations, form of address, polite expressions

An application is an official document, written to a specific institution or official in the name of a person with a request, proposal or complaint. This document is written in an official style and is one of the most widely used and widespread business papers in practice. Writing an application is a widespread phenomenon in society and is used by representatives of various social strata, from schoolchildren to students, managers, farmers, engineers, scientists, entrepreneurs and officials. Thus, almost all members of society are not immune to the process of writing an application.

The prevalence and diversity of the application document are associated with the diversity of its writers and the institutions to which it is sent. These documents can be addressed to school principals, university rectors, enterprise managers, district or regional leadership, in general, to any department or head who has the authority to consider and resolve the applicant's proposal, request or complaint. This shows how wide-ranging and diverse the applications are.

Writing an application is an integral part of any official communication, and its content and form differ fundamentally depending on the purpose. At the same time, applications in French differ not only in grammatical and stylistic terms, but also in language elements that reflect social hierarchy. A correctly

formulated application text increases the chances of receiving a faster and more effective response to the author's appeal.

Regardless of the size, style, and type, any formal letter has its own essential components, the consistency of which is essential for the effective reception and understanding of the letter. Each part has its own function, serving to express the purpose, content, and respect for the person being addressed. These parts are especially important in French-language letters, and they are based on clearly defined rules. The main components of French letters are explained in detail below:

1. Sender's details (Les coordonnées de l'expéditeur)

The personal details of the person or organization writing the letter are given at the beginning of the document. They include:

- Surname and first name: Required to identify the sender.
- Position: If the applicant is applying from an organization or company, this should be indicated.
- Address: The exact address of the sender's place of residence or work.
- Telephone number: Required for communication.
- Email address: To receive a response to the documents electronically.

This information helps to identify the applicant and serves as a basis for communication.

2. Recipient details (Les coordonnées du destinataire)

The full details of the person to whom the application is being sent are written. This section includes the following:

- Surname and first name: The full name of the recipient.
- Position: Indicates whether the recipient is an official or manager in the organization.
- Address: The exact mailing address of the institution.
- Phone number and email address: To contact the applicant if necessary.

This information is important to ensure that the application is sent to the correct recipient.

3. Purpose (L'Objet)

This section is one of the most important sections of the application, in which the writer briefly, clearly and concisely states why he is applying. This section clarifies the type of application and the purpose of its writing. For example, it can be in the form of "Demande d'emploi", "Demande de renseignement" or "Demande de logement".

4. City and date

The place and date of the application are indicated. This section serves to determine the time relevance of the document. The date increases the level of formality of any document and is important for future use. For example: Samarcande, le 15 juillet.

5. Form of address (Forme d'appel)

In this section, the applicant addresses the recipient respectfully. For example, forms of address such as "Monsieur", "Madame" or "Cher Directeur" are used. In French, the form of address is especially important and is selected depending on the title and social status of the recipient.

6. Main text (Le texte principal)

The content of the application is described in detail in this section. In this section, the purpose of the application, reasons for the application, information to be attached to the document and other necessary details are written. The text should be written in a simple, clear and understandable way. It is recommended to avoid excessive emotional expressions or ambiguity in sentences.

7. Politeness Form (Formule de politesse)

In formal applications, it is important to express respect and courtesy. In this part, the writer expresses gratitude for receiving and considering his application and expresses his respect. In French, this part is more complex and uses phrases such as "Veuillez agréer, Monsieur/Madame, l'expression de ma haute consideration".

8. Signature (Signature)

The final part of the application is the signature, which is placed by the person or representative of the organization writing the document. The signature ensures the formality and reliability of the application.

Any formal application is built on the basis of these necessary parts, and the correct consistency of these parts is important for the effective reception and understanding of the application. In particular, applications written in French reflect not only grammar and style through these parts, but also social respect and hierarchical relationships. Therefore, writing each section carefully and clearly ensures that the applicant successfully achieves his goal.

The politeness form (la formule de politesse) is of great importance in application texts, which depends on the person to whom the application is being written. These forms not only reflect the requirements of etiquette, but also indicate the hierarchical relationship between the applicant and the recipient. The correct choice of the politeness form is an important factor in the effective reception of the application.

The following expressions are widely used in official applications written in French:

- The phrase “Veillez agréer” is used in a more elegant and formal manner than the phrases “Je vous prie d’agréer” or “Agréez”.
- The phrase “...l’expression de ma haute considération” is used when addressing a person of high social status.
- The phrase “...l’assurance de ma haute considération” is used when addressing a person of equal status.

Such phrases indicate the degree of respect of the addressee for the addressee. This ensures that the written address is complete in content and form, taking into account hierarchical differences.

Various phrases and stable devices are used to indicate the degree of respect of the addressee for the addressee. The following are the different degrees of respect and their hierarchical order:

Veillez agréer mes salutations les meilleures
Veillez agréer mes salutations distinguées
Veillez agréer mes salutations respectueuses
Veillez agréer l’assurance de mes sentiments les meilleurs
Veillez agréer l’assurance de mes sentiments distingués
Veillez agréer l’assurance de mes sentiments respectueux
Veillez agréer l’assurance de ma haute considération
Veillez agréer l’assurance de ma plus haute considération
Veillez agréer l’assurance de ma parfaite considération
Veillez agréer l’assurance de ma considération distinguée
Veillez agréer l’assurance de ma considération très distinguée

These phrases are chosen according to the title and social status of the person being addressed.

In French applications, the form of politeness reflects not only the content and style of the application, but also the hierarchical relationship between the applicant and the recipient. The use of expressions that express respect and politeness by the applicant helps to achieve his goal faster. In particular, when addressing persons of higher status, the use of elegant and formal expressions is preferred, and when addressing a person of equal status, simpler but respectful styles are preferred.

Although applications written in French are similar in form, there are significant differences in their content. These differences depend not only on the social status of the applicant and the recipient, but also on the correct choice of

the form of politeness. The choice of words and expressions in the application texts, understanding their social and pragmatic meanings, allows the writer of the application to achieve his goal faster. Therefore, the correct use of politeness forms is considered an integral part of the culture of official correspondence.

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